

Idea of Cubic Expectation and Derivation of Its Definition

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Abstract – In continuation to the concepts of arithmetic expectation, geometric expectation, harmonic expectation and quadratic expectation, concept of cubic expectation has been introduced in this article and defined in a similar manner on the basis of cubic mean. This article describes the concept and definition of cubic expectation.

Keywords: Random Variable, Cubic Expectation, Concept, Definition.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of expectation associated to a random variable, which was originated in the middle of the 17th century, was introduced as weighted average of the possible values assumed by the random variable with their respective probabilities as corresponding weights [1, 27]. At first, it was defined as the weighted arithmetic mean of the possible values assumed by the random variable with their respective probabilities as corresponding weights and termed as mathematical expectation [4, 18, 22, 26] later termed as arithmetic expectation [7] since it is based on the oldest and widely used measure of average namely arithmetic mean [5, 23]. Later on, three other concepts of measure of expectation had been introduced on the basis of geometric mean [5, 24], harmonic mean [5, 25] and quadratic mean (or root mean square) [3, 15, 17, 26] and consequently respective definitions were formulated which were respectively termed as geometric expectation [7, 9], harmonic expectation [7, 9] and quadratic expectation [8, 9]. In this connection, it is to be mentioned that it can also be possible to derive a measure of expectation with the help of other measures of average. That is why the same has here been attempted on the basis of cubic mean [12, 21]. In continuation to the concepts of arithmetic expectation, geometric expectation, harmonic expectation and quadratic expectation, concept of cubic expectation has been introduced in this article and defined in a similar manner on the basis of cubic mean. This article describes the concept and definition of cubic expectation.

2. CUBIC EXPECTATION OF A RANDOM VARIABLE

Let us consider a discrete finite random variable.

Suppose a real valued discrete random variable X assumes the values

$$x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$$

so that N values constitute the universe/population of the variable X .

Then the cubic mean [12, 21] of X , denoted by $C(X) = C(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$, is defined by

$$C(X) = \left\{ \frac{1}{N} (x_1^3 + x_2^3 + \dots + x_N^3) \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

This is the population cubic mean or the universe cubic mean of X .

On the other hand, if the values of X correspond to the respective weights

$$w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N$$

then, $C(X) = C(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N)$, will be weighted cubic mean of X and is accordingly defined by

$$C(X) = \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_i} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i x_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Now suppose, X assumes the values

$$x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N$$

with respective probabilities

$$p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N$$

Automatically, $\sum_{i=1}^N p_i = 1$

Then $C(X)$, in this case, will be the weighted cubic mean of X with the probabilities as the respective weights of its respective possible values and accordingly is defined by

$$C(X) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N p_i x_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Since it describes the weighted cubic mean of all possible values of X with respective probabilities as the weights of the respective values, it can be regarded as the cubic expectation of X . Thus, cubic expectation can be defined as follows:

Definition (2.1):

If a real valued random variable X assumes the values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N with respective probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N , then the cubic expectation of X , denoted by $E_C(X)$, is defined by

$$E_C(X) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N p_i x_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{2.1}$$

Now, if X is a real valued discrete random variable assuming the countable infinite (denumerable) values

$$x_1, x_2, \dots$$

with respective probabilities

$$p_1, p_2, \dots$$

then for the existence of cubic expectation of X , the term

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i x_i^3$$

must converge to a finite number.

Definition (2.2):

If X is a real valued discrete random variable assuming the countable infinite (denumerable) values x_1, x_2, \dots with respective probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots , then the cubic expectation of X , denoted by $E_C(X)$, is defined by

$$E_C(X) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i x_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{2.2}$$

provided $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i x_i^3$ is convergent and is a finite number.

Now, suppose that X , instead of discrete, is a continuous random variable assuming values in the real valued interval

$$(a, b) \text{ or } [a, b) \text{ or } (a, b] \text{ or } [a, b]$$

where each a & b of may be finite or infinite,

with probability density function $f(x)$.

Since the possible values in an interval is uncountable & infinite, the weighted cubic mean of these values is to be obtained by integration.

Accordingly, $E_c(X)$ in this case is to be defined by

$$E_c(X) = \left\{ \int_a^b x^3 f(x) dx \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Definition (2.3):

If X is a continuous random variable assuming real values in the intervals

$$(a, b) \text{ or } [a, b) \text{ or } (a, b] \text{ or } [a, b]$$

where a, b may be finite or infinite,

having probability density function $f(x)$,

then cubic expectation of X , denoted by $E_c(X)$, can be defined by

$$E_c(X) = \left\{ \int_a^b x^3 f(x) dx \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{2.3}$$

3. CUBIC EXPECTATION OF FUNCTION OF A RANDOM VARIABLE

If $\phi(X)$ is a function of the real valued random variable X then proceeding with the same logic the cubic expectation of, denoted by $E_c\{\phi(X)\}$, can be defined as follows:

Definition (3.1):

If a real valued random variable X assumes the values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N with respective probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots, p_N , then the cubic expectation of a function $\phi(X)$ of X , denoted by $E_c\{\phi(X)\}$, can be defined by

$$E_c\{\phi(X)\} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^N p_i \{\phi(x_i)\}^3 \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{3.1}$$

Definition (3.2):

If X is a real valued discrete random variable assuming countable infinite (denumerable) values x_1, x_2, \dots with respective probabilities p_1, p_2, \dots , then the cubic expectation of a function $\phi(X)$ of X , denoted by $E_c\{\phi(X)\}$, can be defined by

$$E_c\{\phi(X)\} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i \{\phi(x_i)\}^3 \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{3.2}$$

provided $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i \{\phi(x_i)\}^3$ is convergent and is a finite number.

Definition (3.3):

If X is a continuous random variable assuming real values in the intervals

$$(a, b) \text{ or } [a, b) \text{ or } (a, b] \text{ or } [a, b]$$

where a b may be finite or infinite,

having probability density function $f(x)$,

the cubic expectation of a function $\varphi(x)$ of X , denoted by $E_c\{\varphi(x)\}$, can be defined by

$$E_c\{\varphi(x)\} = \left[\int_a^b \{\varphi(x_i)\}^3 f(x_i) dx \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{3.3}$$

4. RELATION BETWEEN CUBIC AND ARITHMETIC EXPECTATIONS

Arithmetic expectation $[7, 9]$ of random variable X , denoted by $E_A(X)$, is defined by

$$E_A(X) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i x_i$$

when X is finite

and by

$$E_A(X) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i x_i$$

when X is countable infinite (denumerable)

and also, by

$$E_A(X) = \int_a^b x \cdot f(x) dx$$

when X is continuous.

Similarly, the arithmetic expectation of a function $\varphi(x)$ of X , denoted by $E_A\{\varphi(x)\}$, is defined by

$$E_A\{\varphi(x)\} = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i x_i$$

when X is finite

and by

$$E_A\{\varphi(x)\} = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} p_i x_i$$

when X is countable infinite (denumerable)

and also, by

$$E_A\{\varphi(x)\} = \int_a^b x \cdot f(x) dx$$

when X is continuous.

Putting

$$\varphi(x) = x^3$$

in any of the three definitions of $E_A\{\varphi(x)\}$ and in any of the three definitions of $E_C\{\varphi(x)\}$, it is obtained that

$$\{E_c(X)\}^3 = E_A(X^3) \text{ or } E_c(X) = \{E_A(X^3)\}^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{4.1}$$

Thus, cubic expectation of a random variable X is the cube root of arithmetic expectation of its cube (i.e. X^3).

Similarly, putting

$$\varphi(X) = \{h(X)\}^3$$

in any of the three definitions of $E_A\{\varphi(X)\}$ and in any of the three definitions of $E_C\{\varphi(X)\}$, it is obtained that

$$[E_C\{h(X)\}]^3 = E_A[\{h(X)\}^3] \text{ or } E_C\{h(X)\} = E_A[\{h(X)\}^3]^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{4.2}$$

$$\text{i.e. } [E_C\{\varphi(X)\}]^3 = E_A[\{\varphi(X)\}^3] \text{ or } E_C\{\varphi(X)\} = E_A[\{\varphi(X)\}^3]^{\frac{1}{3}} \tag{4.3}$$

i.e. the cubic expectation of a function $\varphi(X)$ of X is the cube root of arithmetic expectation of the cube of $\varphi(X)$ i.e. of $\{\varphi(X)\}^3$.

Thus, the following relationship, mentioned as theorem, between cubic expectation and arithmetic expectation has been obtained:

Theorem (4.1):

“The cubic expectation of a random variable X is the cube root of the arithmetic expectation of its cube i.e. of X^3 and also the cubic expectation of a function $\varphi(X)$ of a random variable X is the cube root of the arithmetic expectation of the cube of $\varphi(X)$ i.e. of $\{\varphi(X)\}^3$.”

4.1 Numerical Example

Let us consider the example of probability distribution of number of rainy days at New Delhi in the month June, shown in Table – 4.1, discussed in an earlier study [7, 8] where arithmetic expectation, geometric expectation, harmonic expectation and quadratic expectation of number of rainy days in the month June at New Delhi were found to be

4.53125, 4.0548509573441987687123105790392, 3.4579759862778730703259005145797

& 4.9212549212573818873031465305075

respectively.

Table –4.1:

June	
Number/Interval of Rainy Days	Probability of occurrence
1	0.0625
2	0.09385
[3, 5]	0.5625

[6 , 8]	0.25
9	0.03125
> 9	0

The values of $p_i x_i^3$ have been found as follows:

Table –4.2:

Number/Interval of Rainy Days	Mid value (x_i)	Value of $p_i x_i^3$
1	1	0.0625
2	2	0.75
3 – 5	4	36
6 – 8	7	85.75
9	9	22.78125
Total	23	145.34375

Applying the above formula, the cubic expectation of number of rainy days in the month June at New Delhi has been found to be

$$5.2577361382748444625896679373977$$

5. CONCLUSION

The cubic mean (or root mean cube) is a type of mathematical average that is particularly important for analysing data related to volume, 3D structures, and physical processes where values increase proportional to the cube of a dimension [21].

Cubic mean {also known as root mean} is a significant measure of average due to its importance and applications in various fields like

Biology (Morphometric): where it is used to measure the mean dimensions of spherical bacteria and other approximately spheroidal organisms,

Engineering (Life Expectancy of Parts): where it is used in predicting the life expectancy of machine parts,

Wind Energy Analysis: where it is used as a measure of local potential for wind energy,

Physical Sciences: where it is useful in applications involving 3D modelling and calculations of volumetric data

and many other [2 , 6 , 14 , 19, 20 , 21].

Consequently, cubic expectation like arithmetic expectation, geometric expectation, harmonic expectation & quadratic expectation has become a significant concept in analysis of data. It is to be noted that expectation is a theoretical entity whose value is usually unknown and is to be estimated from data

available in sample. One criterion/quality of a good estimate is unbiasedness which is defined on the basis of expectation of estimator [16]. Therefore, cubic expectation can lead to make a concept of cubic unbiasedness of estimator and to define it by the similar logic which was used in making concepts as well as in defining of arithmetic unbiasedness, geometric unbiasedness, harmonic unbiasedness & quadratic unbiasedness of estimator [10, 11, 13].

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